

THE ROLE OF SCHOOL PSYCHOLOGISTS IN ADOLESCENT SUPPORT SYSTEMS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF KAZAKHSTAN AND CHINA

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***Аннотация.** С социальным развитием проблемы психического здоровья подростков растет роль школьных психологов в системах школьной службы психического здоровья. Поэтому в этом исследовании используются анкеты и полуструктурированные интервью для анализа роли школьных психологов в системах поддержки психического здоровья подростков в Казахстане и Китае, а также влияние различных факторов, и предлагаются целевые предложения. Результаты показывают, что казахстанские психологи обладают сильной кросс-культурной адаптивностью и подчеркивают сотрудничество с учителями. Система службы психического здоровья Китая имеет высокую степень институционализации, и ее система подготовки психологов относительно завершена. Однако обе страны сталкиваются с такими проблемами, как нехватка психологов, недостаточное сотрудничество учителей и растущие психологические потребности среди учащихся. Эти результаты могут послужить основой для повышения эффективности систем школьной службы психического здоровья.*

***Ключевые слова:** школьные психологи; психическое здоровье подростков; сравнительные исследования; педагогическая психология.*

***Abstract.** With social development, adolescent mental health issues are on the rise, making the role of school psychologists in school mental health service systems increasingly important. Therefore, this study uses questionnaires and semi-structured interviews to analyze the role of school psychologists in the mental health support systems for adolescents in Kazakhstan and China, as well as the impact of various factors, and proposes targeted suggestions. The results show that Kazakhstani psychologists have strong cross-cultural adaptability and emphasize teacher collaboration and practical application. China's mental health service system has a high degree of institutionalization, and its psychologist training system is relatively complete. However, both countries face challenges such as a shortage of psychologists, insufficient teacher cooperation, and increasing psychological needs among students. These findings can serve as a basis for improving the scientific rigor and practicality of school mental health service systems.*

Key words: *School psychologists; adolescent mental health; comparative studies; educational psychology.*

Introduction. Adolescent mental health issues have become a widespread phenomenon globally. A 2021 report by the World Health Organization stated that approximately 20% of adolescents experience mental health problems during their formative years, and school psychologists are a crucial part of this group, bearing the heavy responsibility of safeguarding mental health (Fagan and Wise, 2007). Their duties extend beyond student assessment and counseling; they also include preventative mental health education, training mental health teachers, intervention in student crisis events, and multidisciplinary collaboration (NASP, 2020). While Kazakhstan and China share some commonalities in education, their development of mental health services differs. China has implemented a mental health education system under the framework of "reducing education costs and improving moral character" and "promoting all-round development in education, intellectual, physical, aesthetic, and labor education," In 2016, mental health education in my country was truly incorporated into the curriculum and became an independent subject.while Kazakhstan has its own unique experiences in integrating educational psychology and providing cross-cultural psychological services (Nurmatov, 2018). This study, based on social ecology theory and the MTSS (Multi-Level Support System), explores how school psychologists influence adolescent mental health in the micro and external social environments, and analyzes the differences in systems and practices between China and Kazakhstan through a comparative analysis.

Significance of the study: within the school psychological support system, this study compares and analyzes the work of school psychologists in supporting adolescents in Kazakhstan and China, which has significant theoretical and practical value. Using the social ecology theory of complementary internal structures (Bronfenbrenner, 1979), the MTSS (Multi-Level Support System), and the NASP (National Association for the Study of School Psychologists' Professional Functions) as the theoretical framework, this study analyzes the role of school psychologists in the school psychological support system from a multi-system, cross-border perspective, employing a social systems view. By comparing the differences between the two countries at the microsystem (school), mesosystem (home-school), exosystem (policy-resources allocation), and macrosystem (culture value) levels, the study enriches the theoretical foundation of cross-cultural research in school psychology and provides new foundations and examples for school psychological education in different backgrounds in both countries.

Research purpose: This study uses a hybrid research approach combining questionnaires and semi-structured interviews to compare the differences between school psychologists in Kazakhstan and China in terms of role positioning, work content, and work effectiveness. For example, it examines the characteristics of the role of school psychologists in psychological support, intervention practices, and student needs, the challenges and lessons learned in each country, and the actual effects on students' mental health. It also provides reference suggestions for school mental health education in my country.

Research hypothesis: 1. There is a significant difference in the level of support for school counselors between Kazakhstani and Chinese students. 2. The higher the level of professional training of psychologists, the more conducive it is to the provision of corresponding psychological services; similarly, the more actively the role of counseling is promoted to students, the better they will be attracted to try and utilize psychological services.

As an important member of the school mental health support system, school psychologists conduct psychological assessments of students, provide individual counseling, intervene in crises for students and teachers, conduct home-school communication with parents and students, and help teachers deal with their psychological problems. By comparing Kazakhstan and China, a more comprehensive understanding of the role of school psychologists in the school adolescent mental health support system can be obtained.

This is explained with reference to social ecology theory (Bronfenbrenner, 1979), the Multilevel Intervention System (MTSS), and the National Academy of Social Sciences (NASP) model of the professional functions of school psychologists.

Interpersonal relationships are divided into four hierarchically layered environmental systems. These systems influence each other. This theory, proposed and refined by Urie Bronfenbrenner, is now widely accepted as the leading theory in the field of developmental psychology.

Research Methods: Mixed Approach – Questionnaire Survey, Semi-structured Interviews, Analysis Methods: 1. Qualitative Research: Thematic Analysis, NVivo Software Coding Analysis

2. Quantitative Analysis: Between-Group Comparison (Reliability Analysis, Validity Analysis, t-test), Chi-square Test

This research constructs a theoretical framework that integrates Bronfenbrenner's social ecology theory, the Multilevel Support System (MTSS), and the NASP (National Association for the Study of School Psychologists) professional function model to theoretically build a school psychological support system. Yuri Bronfenbrenner proposed that interpersonal relationships are divided into four hierarchically layered environmental systems. These systems influence each other. Combining this theory with psychology, as social ecology theory emphasizes, adolescent development is influenced by multiple layers of environment, including microsystems, mesosystems, exosystems, and macrosystems (Bronfenbrenner, 1979).

From an ecological perspective, applying the MTSS in practice can enhance the psychological services function of schools. The first level provides general and comprehensive care, such as basic psychological education and a good campus environment to care for and protect all students. The second level provides specialized and precise assistance, such as individual and group counseling. The third level involves more effective and intensive interventions, such as referrals to professional counseling and psychotherapy, and provides different activity spaces for students when needed. (1979). *The Ecology of Human Development: Experiments by Nature and Design*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press. ISBN 0-674-22457-4

Simultaneously, the NASP model is used to explore the differences and similarities between the two approaches, identify the strengths of Chinese school psychologists, and, combined with NAIP, focus the effectiveness of Chinese school psychologists on student support systems. The NASP Practice Model (2020) further clarifies the basic professional functions of school psychologists in this multi-system, multi-level structure.

This study combines these three elements as a basic theoretical framework, which can be used to clarify the role positioning, service practices, and support effectiveness of school psychologists in Kazakhstan and China within the multi-layered school system. It can also establish a consistent analytical scale and theoretical basis for comparative cultural school psychological services.

Results Analysis: A questionnaire survey was conducted in Kazakhstan and China. The number of participants was 54 in Kazakhstan and 54 in China.

1. Quantitative Analysis

1.1.1 Reliability Analysis

First, a reliability analysis was conducted on the questionnaire data from Kazakhstan. This study used the scale's reliability analysis results, specifically including the Cronbach's alpha coefficient and the number of items. The analysis showed that the scale's Cronbach's alpha coefficient was 0.727, calculated from 13 items. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient measures the internal consistency of a scale; generally, a coefficient greater than 0.7 indicates internal consistency. In this case, the coefficient was 0.727, which is greater than 0.7. Therefore, the scale has a high level of reliability in measuring target constructs and can be applied to this study.

Table 1 Reliability Analysis

Kronbach's Alpha	number of terms
0.727	13

1.1.2 Validity Analysis

Table 2 Validity Analysis

KMO Sampling Adequacy Measure		0.740
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	210.505
	Degrees of Freedom (df)	78
	Significance	<.001

This study used the KMO sampling appropriateness measure and Bartlett's test of sphericity to validate the validity of the scale. The results showed that the KMO statistic was 0.740, indicating a certain degree of correlation among the variables, and that the sample data was suitable for factor analysis. The approximate chi-square value of the Bartlett's test of sphericity was 210.505, reaching statistical significance at 78 degrees of freedom ($p < 0.001$). This result rejected the null hypothesis that the variables were uncorrelated, further confirming the existence of a shared factor structure among the observed variables. These quantitative indicators collectively demonstrate that the current research data is appropriate for factor analysis, the scale used has good construct validity, and it can effectively measure the target construct.

1.2.1 Reliability Analysis

A reliability and validity analysis was conducted using questionnaire data from 54 Chinese participants, as shown in the figure below:

Table 3 Reliability Analysis

Kronbach's Alpha	number of terms
0.936	13

This study used Cronbach's alpha coefficient to test the reliability of the measurement tool. As shown in the table above, the data analysis results of 13 measurement items show that the overall Cronbach's alpha coefficient reached 0.936, significantly higher than the generally accepted benchmark of 0.7 in social science research (Nunnally, 1978), and also far higher than the excellent standard of 0.8. This result indicates that the scale has excellent internal consistency, a high degree of correlation among the measurement items, and statistically

excellent data reliability. Such a high reliability coefficient ($\alpha > 0.9$) means that the measurement tool has good construct validity and can stably and accurately reflect the essential characteristics of the research subjects, which provides a solid data quality guarantee for subsequent analysis.

1.2.2 Validity Analysis

Table 4 Validity Analysis

KMO Sampling Adequacy Measure		0.922
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	414.096
	Degrees of Freedom (df)	78
	Significance	<.001

The study first validated the suitability of factor analysis using the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure (KMO) and Bartlett's test of sphericity. The results showed that the KMO value was 0.922, significantly higher than the 0.7 threshold proposed by Kaiser (Kaiser, 1974), indicating strong partial correlation among variables, making it suitable for factor analysis. The approximate chi-square value of the Bartlett's test of sphericity was 414.096 (degrees of freedom = 78, $p < 0.001$), strongly rejecting the null hypothesis of independence among variables and confirming the existence of significant shared variance in the observed data (Hair et al., 2019). The significance of these two tests ($KMO > 0.8$ and Bartlett's $p < 0.001$) together constitutes the statistical premise for factor analysis.

1.3.1 Kazakhstan Gender T-test

The t-test was conducted on both countries from a gender perspective to analyze whether there are significant differences in gender differences between Kazakhstan and China in the support system for adolescents by school psychologists.

Table 5. Kazakhstan Sex T-test Table

	gender	N	Mean	Standard deviation	t-value	p-value
5、 Is the school's counseling room a comfortable and pleasant environment?	male	27	2.37	1.275	1.583	0.12
	female	27	1.89	0.934		
7、 When I'm in a bad mood, I'll consider seeking help from a counselor.	male	27	2.44	1.188	1.474	0.147
	female	27	2.04	0.808		
...

This study used an independent samples t-test to compare and analyze the differences in attitudes and behaviors related to mental health between male and female students. The sample consisted of 27 males and 27 females, totaling 54 participants. The test covered multiple variables, including evaluations of the school's counseling environment, willingness to seek help, perception of psychological resources, stress experience, and emotion management. Overall, the analysis showed no statistically significant differences between male and female students on most variables, but one variable reached marginal significance.

On the item "I will actively participate in school mental health activities," the gender difference was statistically significant ($t = 2.026$, $p = 0.05$). The mean participation willingness of female students ($M = 1.56$, $SD = 0.70$) was significantly lower than that of male students ($M = 2.15$, $SD = 1.35$), indicating that women are more inclined to actively participate in school mental health activities. Furthermore, there were no significant differences between male and female students in stress-related variables, such as "I often feel a lot of academic pressure" (male: $M = 2.67$, $SD = 1.27$; female: $M = 2.59$, $SD = 1.45$; $t = 0.200$, $p = 0.842$) and "I often experience insomnia and poor sleep due to stress" (male: $M = 2.93$, $SD = 1.30$; female: $M = 3.15$, $SD = 1.46$; $t = -0.591$, $p = 0.557$). Regarding emotion management, the mean for "I can effectively manage my emotions" was exactly the same in both male and female groups (male: $M = 2.67$, $SD = 1.44$; female: $M = 2.67$, $SD = 1.33$; $t = 0.000$, $p = 1.000$), further supporting the absence of gender differences. For the other variables, the p-values were all higher than 0.05, indicating that there were no significant gender differences in these dimensions.

1.3.2 Chinese Gender T-test

Table 6. T-test on gender in China

	gender	N	Mean	Standard deviation	t-value	p-value
5、 Is the school's counseling room a comfortable and pleasant environment?	male	23	2.48	1.275	0.073	0.942
	female	31	2.45	1.362		
7、 When I'm in a bad mood, I'll consider seeking help from a counselor.	male	23	2.65	1.265	1.526	0.133
	female	31	2.13	1.231		
...

This study used an independent samples t-test to explore gender differences across various psychologically relevant items. The sample included 23 male and 31 female participants, covering multiple dimensions such as perceived psychological counseling environment, willingness to seek help, evaluation of psychological resources, perceived stress, and emotion

management. Statistical results showed that gender differences were not statistically significant in most items ($P > 0.05$). Overall, these findings suggest that gender differences are relatively limited across the investigated psychological health dimensions, with only parental support attitudes showing a significant difference.

In summary, t-tests were conducted separately for samples from China and Kazakhstan to compare scores across different genders on psychological health dimensions. The results showed no significant gender differences in most dimensions between the two countries, indicating that gender differences in perceived school psychological support, level of psychological distress, emotion management, and self-efficacy are generally small. Male and female students scored largely the same on these psychological indicators, reflecting that gender is not a major factor influencing these core psychological variables.

2. Chi-square test

2.1 grade

Table 7 Cross Table

		Grade			Total
		Junior High School	Senior High School	College/University	
Questionnaire belongs to	China	7	11	36	54
	Kazakhstan	5	43	6	54
total		12	54	42	108

Table 8 Chi-square test

	Value	Degrees of freedom	Asymptotic significance (two-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	40.725a	2	<.001
Likelihood Ratio	44.376	2	<.001
Linear-by-Linear Association	17.009	1	<.001
Valid Cases	108		

The chi-square test results showed a Pearson chi-square value of 40.725 with 2 degrees of freedom, and an asymptotic significance p-value less than 0.001. The likelihood ratio test result was 44.376 with 2 degrees of freedom, and the p-value was also less than 0.001. The linear association test result was 17.009 with 1 degree of freedom, and the p-value was also less than 0.001. All three tests indicate a highly significant difference in the grade distribution between the two countries' samples. This statistical result rejects the null hypothesis that the grade distributions are independent between the two countries' samples, reflecting fundamentally different structural characteristics in the educational stage composition of the two samples. This difference in distribution may stem from the characteristics of the two countries' education systems or the actual sampling process. When conducting cross-national comparative analyses, the potential impact of this structural difference on the research results needs to be considered.

2.2 age

Table 9 Cross Table

		age		Total
		12-15	15-18	
Questionnaire belongs to	China	16	38	54
	Kazakhstan	3	51	54
total		19	89	108

Table 10 Chi-square test

	Value	Degrees of freedom	Asymptotic significance (two-sided)	Exact significance (two-sided)	Exact significance (Unilateral)
Pearson Chi-Square	10.794a	1	0.001		
Continuity Correction	9.197	1	0.002		
Likelihood Ratio	11.671	1	<.001		
Fisher’s Exact Test				0.002	<.001
Linear-by-Linear Association	10.694	1	0.001		
Valid Cases	108				

The chi-square test results showed significant and systematic differences in age structure between the Kazakhstani and Chinese samples. This finding has substantial implications for studying the role of school psychologists in adolescent support systems. Firstly, age is a key factor influencing students' mental health. Significant differences were found in the level of trust children of different age groups have in school counselors across various perspectives. In conclusion, the statistical significance of these age-related differences reminds researchers that age must be considered in cross-national comparisons of school mental health support systems. This ensures that the assessment of the role of school psychologists more accurately reflects actual developmental differences and makes the research conclusions more valid and comparable.

Analysis based on the NVivo matrix coding model reveals significant differences between Kazakhstan and China in the demand structure and service focus of school psychologists regarding adolescent support. Kazakhstani students' main psychological concerns are concentrated in emotion regulation, school adjustment, and interpersonal conflict. They have higher trust in school counselors and a significantly stronger willingness to seek help compared to Chinese students. School counselors also play a more emotionally supportive role, emphasizing listening, empathy, and adaptation guidance. In contrast, Chinese students' concerns are more significantly influenced by academic pressure, academic anxiety, and family expectations. Their help-seeking behavior is constrained by cultural shame and unfamiliarity with mental health services, resulting in lower support levels. Chinese school psychologists' work leans more towards stress management, psychoeducation, and functional intervention, while Kazakhstan places greater emphasis on humanistic emotional support. The matrix model comparison reveals that the differences between the two countries stem from different education

systems, cultural values, family expectations, and the allocation of mental health service resources, reflecting their respective representative mental health support ecosystem structures.

In summary, this study, through questionnaires and semi-structured interviews with school psychologists, examined how they contribute to the healthy development of adolescents within school support systems, their practical work, and the challenges they currently face. School psychologists play a vital role in this regard in both Kazakhstan and China, but both face similar challenges such as insufficient resources, unclear responsibilities, and limited opportunities for professional development. Regarding the interim results, the sample has certain limitations, primarily consisting of students and teachers at various stages, and it cannot fully represent the entire group. However, the overall sample is still quite meaningful, and future work could expand the sample size to a wider scope.

In conclusion, school psychologists are a crucial force in adolescent mental health support abroad, but certain challenges remain in both countries, requiring further improvement. This study provides policymakers with insights from three aspects: policy, resource allocation, and professional standards. For China, it is necessary to reduce the administrative burden on schools, empower school psychologists, and implement in-depth intervention models. For Kazakhstan, a comprehensive and systematic framework for mental health services is needed, including a professional talent training system, a supervision system, and school-based service standards.

Comparative research can yield valuable insights into the role of school psychologists and provide valuable references for the development of school mental health service systems in both countries. Future research could further incorporate longitudinal data to examine the long-term impact of mental health service interventions on students' psychological development and academic performance.

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